

IEA Wind Task 52 – Summer Game

18 m/s Hurdles Report

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Anemometers are still widely used in power curve tests and many other cases that need to assess wind around turbines. But with the increasing of rotor diameter, the result of one anemometer shows many limits in describing a huge rotor area.

Figure 1 Difference between rotor average and anemometer wind speed

Wind speed from anemometer can be similar with rotor average wind speed in frequency domain by using a low-pass filter. But the error between them is still increasing with the increasing of rotor diameter.

Figure 2 wind speed error of different rotor size

Nacelle LiDAR is a better equipment to measure the wind in larger rotor plane than an anemometer. Pulsed nacelle LiDARs can measure many points along the beams at the same time, which provides more details to calculate rotor average wind speed with higher accuracy.

Figure 3 Measurement points of pulsed nacelle LiDAR

Although nowadays nacelle LiDARs are widely used, the Rotor Effective Wind Speed (REWS) from LiDAR is not as accurate as we thought due to the limited number of measure points. According to Taylor's frozen hypothesis, multi-gates wind speed results of different distance can be arranged in one plane when wind direction is along the nacelle (most time when turbines run normally). Then there will be much more data at the same time and get REWS with much higher accuracy.

Figure 4 multi-gates LiDAR result

Figure 5 Wind speed error of LiDAR and anemometer

REWS is calculated by a lot of points, and the correlation between points decreases by the distance between them. As a result, the fluctuation of REWS is lower when the area is larger. For the same reason, LiDAR-REWS has higher high-frequency components than real REWS, because LiDAR focal points can't fill all the rotor area. It's a better way to use a low-pass filter to reduce this error than increasing more points. Using multi-gates points and a suitable filter, the error of REWS will reduce 45% than using one gate and reduce 65% than using anemometers.

Figure 6 error of different LiDAR range and rotor size

$$\text{Coh}(r, f) = \exp \left[-12 \left((f \cdot r / V_{ref})^2 + (0.12 r / L_w)^2 \right)^{0.5} \right] \quad (\text{B.16})$$

where

$\text{Coh}(r, f)$ is the coherence function defined by the complex magnitude of the cross-spectral density of the longitudinal wind velocity components at two spatially separated points divided by the autospectrum function;

r is the magnitude of the projection of the separation vector between the two points on to a plane normal to the average wind direction;

Figure 7 Exponential coherence model (IEC-61400, B.16)

For the same reason, it will be a better LiDAR-REWS when the beam angles and gate distances of a pulsed nacelle LiDAR match the rotor size. Usually, the gate distances can be changed by software, so it's much easier for it to fit the rotor size. In this case, we choose 10 gates between 70 to 280 meters to fit a 240m rotor diameter. In addition, since the correlation of wind speed between two points decreases by distance and the distances between LiDAR focal points are different, suitable weighting factor of every LiDAR focal point contributes to the final 10% increase of REWS accuracy.